

Research Article

Dragon Fruit Peel for Cosmetic Purposes

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Abstract: *The cosmetic industry has depended so long on synthetic antioxidants such as butylated hydroxytoluene (BHT) and butylated hydroxyanisole (BHA). These compounds help enhance product stability and protect the skin against oxidative damage. The way these compounds work is by neutralizing free radicals. Free radicals accelerate skin aging and cause cellular damage. Although these compounds are effective, significant health concerns have been raised about the use of synthetic antioxidants. Through numerous studies, prolonged exposure to these compounds has been reported to cause dangerous side effects such as skin irritation, allergic reactions, and even potential long-term toxicological risks. From these changes, scientists and cosmetic developers started to research the antioxidant characteristics of plant-based compounds to become an alternative.*

Keywords: dragon fruit; cosmetic; antioxidant.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Over these past few years, the cosmetic industry has been shifting the use of synthetic ingredients to natural and sustainable ingredients. Consumers start to become aware of the side effects of synthetic additives. This increases the demand for plant-based alternatives that are safer and environmentally friendly. One examples of natural sources are fruits and their byproducts, which have been the number one choice in industry (Machado et. al, 2024). This is due to their high content of bioactive compounds and functional benefits. Dragon fruit (*Hylocereus* spp.) peels are an instance of underutilised fruit byproducts. Although having considerable nutritional and phytochemical value, they were usually discarded during processing.

Dragon fruit peel is particularly rich in antioxidants such as flavonoids, polyphenols, and betalains. These are compounds that are well known for their ability to scavenge free radicals, reduce oxidative stress, and delay the signs of aging. With these properties, dragon fruit peels become a potential natural ingredient for cosmetic formulations that aim to protect the skin from environmental damage and maintain its youthful appearance. Not only that, but improved skin tone, elasticity, and overall dermal health can also be contributed to by the antioxidant activity of these compounds (Pandel et. al, 2013).

This project aims to explore the potential of antioxidants in powdered dragon fruit peels and assess whether it is suitable for cosmetic applications (Som et. al, 2019). From this, it will highlight a valuable use for agricultural waste and also support the development of greener, more sustainable products in the personal care industry. By using natural byproducts such as dragon fruit peels in

cosmetics formulation, the environmental impact can be reduced by manufacturers. It will also fulfill the growing demand of consumers for clean-label, plant-based ingredients.

Eventually, this project will contribute to the ongoing efforts of innovation in the field of cosmetology with the use of environmentally responsible resources. If successful, the application of powdered dragon fruit peel as an active antioxidant agent will be a gateway to broader utilization of fruit waste in skincare and other personal care products. Since more and more consumers are becoming aware of ingredient safety, demand for natural, skin-friendly, and sustainable alternatives has intensified.

2. METHOD & MATERIAL

This study aims to determine the antioxidant properties of powdered dragon fruit (*Hylocereus* spp.) peel for cosmetic applications. A comprehensive methodology is adopted, including sample preparation, FTIR analysis, UV-Vis spectroscopy combined with the DPPH assay, and Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) to assess the chemical and physical characteristics of the powdered extract. Each step is designed to maximize the accuracy and reproducibility of the data collected, enabling a holistic understanding of the bioactive potential of the dragon fruit peel.

Following cleaning, the peels will be manually sliced into smaller pieces (approximately 2 cm x 2 cm) using a sterilized stainless steel knife. This step aims to increase the surface area for more efficient drying. The sliced peels will then be spread evenly on clean, stainless steel trays and air-dried in a shaded, well-ventilated area for 3 to 5 days. Shaded drying is preferred to preserve heat-sensitive phytochemicals such as anthocyanins and flavonoids. After air drying, to ensure complete moisture removal and prevent microbial growth, the samples will undergo controlled oven-drying at 40°C for 24 hours. The dried peel samples will be ground into fine powder using a laboratory-scale mechanical grinder. The ground material will be sieved through a 60-mesh sieve (250 µm) to achieve a uniform particle size, which is essential for consistency in subsequent analytical procedures. The powdered samples will then be stored in airtight amber glass containers to protect them from light and moisture, and kept in a desiccator at room temperature until further analysis. All tools and containers used during this process will be sterilized to prevent contamination.

3. EXPECTED RESULTS

The purpose of this study was to verify that the presence of bioactive substances like flavonoids, phenolics, and betacyanins in powdered dragon fruit peel results in notable antioxidant qualities. It is expected that FTIR analysis will identify functional groups like hydroxyl and carbonyl groups that are frequently linked to antioxidant activity. According to UV-Vis spectroscopy, the DPPH assay should demonstrate significant free radical scavenging activity, suggesting that the peel extract has potent antioxidant potential. Furthermore, fine surface morphology and particle structure should be revealed by SEM analysis, as these factors may affect how well antioxidants are delivered in cosmetic applications (Ali et. al, 2023). In addition to helping to reduce agricultural waste, the study is anticipated to support the possible use of dragon fruit peel as a sustainable and natural antioxidant source in cosmetic formulations.

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